

ELECTRO-OPTIC SYSTEMS RESEARCH USING THE VARIABLE PARAMETER FLIR

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ABSTRACT

The Air Force has interest in electro-optical systems to perform a variety of missions. Advanced system design often involves research and trade studies to define what parameters are important to a particular application. Usually analysis and computer simulations are used to evaluate system concepts and perform the trades studies. However, the analysis and simulations often suffer from a lack of data needed to validate the models that are used in the studies. An efficient and cost-effective approach to electro-optic system research is to investigate system concepts and sensor components on a generic testbed that can be readily modified for a variety of applications. The Variable Parameter FLIR is a research and development testbed for evaluating systems concepts, testing sensor components, and providing benchmark data for model and figure-of-merit validations. In this paper, we will describe the Variable Parameter FLIR and show how it can be used in electro-optic system research by presenting an example of microscanned imagery.

SECTION I. INTRODUCTION

Several trade-offs and decisions must be made during the course of development of an electro-optical system. Some of the parameters that must be determined are the roles of active or passive channels in the system, what wavelengths will be used, whether the system will be scanning or staring, the field-of-view and the resolution required, and the external constraints imposed by the operating environment. These determinations must all be made in the context of what the final output of the electro-optical system is to be. Is the final output to be a displayed image that is interpreted by a human operator, or does the output of the electro-optical system serve as input to some automated algorithm?

It is often advantageous to perform preliminary studies, either analytical or empirical, to answer some of the questions, but it is not always possible to do so. Either it is too expensive to develop a system dedicated to empirically investigate a single concept, or the analytical models are not sufficiently validated to make them worthwhile. An alternative is to develop a generic system which can be easily modified to investigate the particular components, concepts, and applications of interest. In addition, such a system would allow one to perform trade studies and investigate concepts for overcoming component limitations. Finally, such a system could be used to collect data to validate computer models and simulations. We have developed such a generic system, which is called the Variable Parameter FLIR (VP FLIR). In the next section, we describe the capabilities of the VP FLIR. Section III illustrates how the VP FLIR can be used in systems research. We describe an experiment in microscanning which has been conducted using the system. Microscanning is essentially a method of increasing the sampling frequency of a staring focal plane array at the expense of detector integration time. [1] The results show the reduced aliasing associated with a microscanned system and illustrate how a systems approach can overcome limitations of a single component.

SECTION II. DESCRIPTION OF THE VP FLIR

The VP FLIR is built upon the nucleus of a focal plane array test station developed by Amber Engineering, Inc.[2] In its current configuration, the VP FLIR is capable of accepting input from multiple focal plane arrays at one time. The simultaneous imaging capability eliminates a primary source of uncertainty in experiments which compare different components or concepts. With the capability to image multiple focal plane arrays, comparisons can

be made under identical environmental conditions. Within each imaging channel, there are many parameters that can be varied. These parameters can be grouped in the areas of optics, focal plane array interface electronics (clocks, biases, and data acquisition electronics), data processing hardware, and display electronics. Each of these subsystems will now be described.

Each imaging channel has its own set of optics. The optics can be changed so that good transmission is achieved in either the 3 - 5 micrometer or the 8 - 12 micrometer spectral band. The imaging optics consist of two primary components. A variable f-number optic produces an image at the focal plane array which is housed in a dewar. The aperture stop of the system is typically located at the cold shield in the dewar. However, an external aperture can be changed in size to investigate the effects of variable cold shield efficiency. The size of the stop in the dewar can be varied to produce seven discrete f-numbers in the range $f/1.2$ to $f/5$. The imager has a fixed focal length, but the system focal length can be varied through the use of the second component in the optics train, which is an afocal, zoom system. The zoom can vary the system focal length continuously from one to four times the imager focal length. The advantage of a continuous zoom is that the system focal length can be adjusted so that focal plane arrays with different pixel spacings will all have the same number of pixels across a given field of view. The imager and the afocal zoom have an external entrance and exit pupil, respectively, so that a scan mirror can be incorporated in the optics train. Therefore, either scanned or staring arrays can be imaged by the VP FLIR and the scanning arrays can operate in the time-delay-integration mode. The scan pattern can be easily modified through software using a graphical interface.

A variety of focal plane array materials can be imaged using the VP FLIR. The dewar housing the focal plane arrays can be cooled to temperatures as low as 20° K, allowing the detector elements to be made of a wide range of materials, including HgCdTe, PtSi, InSb, GaAs, and Ga doped Si. The electronics of the VP FLIR can supply a total of 80 clock signals to the multiple focal plane arrays. These clock patterns, too, are generated using software with a graphical interface. Similarly, 30 programmable bias power supplies are under software control. All the software is menu-driven with on-line help. Video buffers are located near the focal plane array output to reduce noise. The output of the video buffers goes to the data acquisition electronics.

There are a total of 16 input channels which feed into the data acquisition electronics, called Pro-View.[3] The 16 channels have a combined 80 MHz

data acquisition rate. Each channel performs a 5 MHz A/D conversion that is 12 bits deep. Each channel also has a nonuniformity correction circuit that can perform a one-point (offset) or a two-point (gain and offset) correction. While the data to form the correction table is collected off-line, the correction to the incoming data is performed in real time. In addition, it is possible to store two nonuniformity correction tables in the channel memory, so that, in conjunction with image processing hardware described below, the nonuniformity table can be corrected in real-time, loaded into the second memory buffer, and then correction can be made using the second buffer. By ping-ponging between the buffers, real-time gain and offset compensation can be performed.

In addition to the gain and offset correction, Pro-View can also perform an intensity transformation using a user-defined table stored in memory. For example, a linear to logarithmic intensity transformation can be performed on the data as it is acquired. The Series 3000 software contains an array calculator which allows arithmetic operations on the image array as a whole. In addition, the array calculator can perform other operations such as calculating mean and variance of the image, as well as performing square and square root operations on the array. The Series 3000 software will also generate histograms and projection plots of image data.

Each channel in the image acquisition electronics of Pro-View contains dual frame buffers. Each buffer consists of 64K of 16 bit memory. The dual frame buffers allows Pro-View to write to one buffer while it is reading out the other buffer. Therefore, differences between the acquired data rate and the display rate can be tolerated. The 16 bit deep memory allows Pro-View to integrate frames of 12 bit deep data from the A/D's. In the frame integration mode, an incoming frame can be subtracted instead of added. Therefore, if a reference source is viewed during the integration process, any offset nonuniformity can be subtracted out of the data.

Digital data can also be input to Pro-View. Sixteen bit digital input, such as from a digital camera, digital signal processor, or digital recording device, bypasses the A/D converters and goes directly into the frame buffers.

The majority of the image processing capability of the VP FLIR resides in the Virtual Processing Element Resource (ViPER) hardware. ViPER is a massively parallel, single instruction/multiple data computing system with multiple processing elements arranged in a two-dimensional matrix. It has a processing speed of 3000 MOPS, and can perform a variety of functions including convolution with arbitrary kernels and upsampling. Other image

processing functions that can be performed include edge enhancement, feature extraction, segmentation, morphological filtering, and object classification.

Image display is accomplished by a second Pro-View system. Up to 1024 X 1024 pixels can be displayed at 25 MHz pixel rates through a high-speed video bus. Dead pixels in the detector array are replaced by nearest neighbors. Pro-View also performs pseudo-color display from one of several palettes, symbolic overlay, and electronic zoom (one pixel mapped to many pixels, or many pixels mapped to one pixel). The displayed pixels are a mapping of the acquired data pixels. The mapping is performed with a user-generated vector table which relates a display pixel with a data pixel. Because of the vector table mapping, the data need not be acquired in the same order in which it is displayed. The vector table feature is especially attractive in display of micro-scanned imagery, which we will discuss in Sec. III. The image data can also be sent to a high bit rate digital recorder instead of a CRT.

The preceding discussion is a brief overview of the capabilities of the VP FLIR. The system was used to perform a preliminary investigation into the improvements in image fidelity associated with microscanning, as will be described next.

SECTION III. ALIASING REDUCTION USING MICROSCANNING

Typical electro-optical systems are sampled data systems because the detection is performed by a discrete number of finite-sized detectors. Therefore, the images produced by electro-optical systems typically contain artifacts that are related to the sampling process. Two of the most common artifacts are blurring and aliasing. Blurring is the loss of fine detail in an image due to the limited spatial frequencies passed by the electro-optical system. Frequently, the limitation in spatial frequency is due to the finite size of the detector. Aliasing is the appearance of one spatial frequency as another spatial frequency. Any spatial frequency greater than half the sampling frequency of the detector mosaic will appear as a frequency less than half the sampling frequency. The process of aliasing is illustrated in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1a, the image is shown along with the sampling matrix that is used to detect the image. For this example, the fundamental spatial frequency of the image is equal to the sampling frequency of the detector mosaic. The output of the detector matrix is shown in Fig. 1b. We see that the output of the detector does not vary from sample to sample, even though the image itself undergoes rapid oscillation. The appearance of a spatial frequency (in Fig. 1a, the spatial frequency equals the sampling frequency) as

Fig. 1. Effect of aliasing. (a) Highly oscillatory image, with a sampling rate equal to the oscillation frequency. (b) Output of sampling system shows no variation.

another spatial frequency (in Fig. 1b, as DC, or zero, frequency) is what is referred to as aliasing. Aliasing can be one of the most significant artifacts in image reconstruction.[4]

One solution to the problem of aliasing is to decrease the spatial frequencies that are passed by the electro-optical system by adjusting the size of the detector so that all the spatial frequencies are less than or equal to half of the sampling frequency of the detector matrix. However, unacceptable blurring of the image can result. Another solution is to increase the sampling rate of the detector matrix. Increasing the number of detectors in the mosaic can be difficult from a fabrication standpoint. Another method of increasing the sampling frequency without increasing the number of detector elements in the mosaic is microscanning, which will now be described.

Consider a detector sampling matrix as illustrated in Fig. 2a. In normal operation, each pixel in the detector array would view a fixed portion of the object. In microscanning, several images of the object are recorded, with the field-of-view of the detector mosaic being shifted by a fraction of a pixel spacing between each recorded image. An example of the shift is illustrated in Fig. 2b. Effectively, the sampling rate across the object has been increased, but the integration time has also changed. Either the frame integration time must increase or the integration time at each position in the microscan must be reduced from the unscanned integration time.

Fig. 2. Illustration of microscanning. (a) Detector sampling matrix superimposed on image. (b) Sampling matrix shifted by half a pixel spacing from position in (a).

We model the effects of microscanning by summing the images produced in each of the microscan steps. For the example considered here, we assume a two by two microscan, that is, a total of four detector positions makes up a single image frame. The analysis is most easily performed in the spatial frequency domain. For a single detector position, the Fourier transform \bar{I} of the image is given by [5]

$$\bar{I}(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{O}((d_x \xi - n), (d_y \eta - m)) \times \text{sinc}((d_x \xi - n), (d_y \eta - m)) \quad (1)$$

where \bar{O} is the object spatial frequency spectrum, d_x and d_y are the sampling periods in the x and y direction (it is assumed that the pixel dimensions equal the pixel spacings), respectively, ξ and η are spatial frequencies in the x and y direction, respectively, and $\text{sinc}(x) = \sin(\pi x)/(\pi x)$. The sinc term is the result of the blurring produced by the finite size of the detector pixel. Aliasing occurs when higher order terms in the summation (m, n not equal to zero) are non-zero within the spatial frequency bandwidth of the display device. Now, if four images are recorded, with the detector mosaic moved by half a pixel spacing between each image, as shown in Fig. 3, then the four images can be combined to form a single frame. The summed image is then given by

Fig. 3. Motion of detector matrix due to microscan step-stare.

$$\bar{I}(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{O}((d_x \xi - n), (d_y \eta - m)) \times \text{sinc}((d_x \xi - n), (d_y \eta - m)) \times (1 + e^{-i\pi n} + e^{-i\pi m} + e^{-i\pi(m+n)}) \quad (2)$$

where the term in brackets is due to the four images recorded to make one frame of data. From inspection of Eq. (2), we see that the effect of microscanning is to cause the term in brackets to be zero for all the nearest-neighbor terms ($m=1, n=1$, or both) to the zeroth order term. This substantially reduces aliasing (overlap of higher order terms on the zeroth order term) in the final image. By comparing Eqs. (1) and (2), we see that the microscan process does not blur the resulting image, since the sinc term which causes the blur is the same for both the unscanned and the microscanned image. Note that the microscan mirror is stationary during the image acquisition so there is no motion blur associated with the mirror.

The VP FLIR was used to experimentally investigate the ability to reduce aliasing with the microscan process. Two 128X128 focal plane arrays were used to simultaneously image a spoke object. The detector elements in each array were made from InSb, and were 40 μm squares on 50 μm spacings in both dimensions. The only difference between the two imaging systems was that one system had a scan mirror in the optics beam train to perform the microscan motion. The integration time of the microscanned image was adjusted so that all four images were collected within a single frame integration time of the non-scanned image. The two images were displayed on a single monitor for comparison. The microscanned image was assembled using the vector table. The four recorded images were stored sequentially in the memory buffer, then a pixel from each of the four images was

mapped to a two by two portion of the displayed image. Figure 4 shows the microscanned and unscanned images. Image artifacts associated with aliasing are clearly evident in the unscanned image. The microscanned image shows much more fidelity in its representation of the true object.

SECTION IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have described a highly flexible testbed, called the VP FLIR, for performing research on electro-optical systems. One of the primary advantages of the system is the ability to simultaneously image multiple focal plane arrays. It is therefore possible to unambiguously characterize the effects of specified parameters within the independent image trains, since all other factors can be made the same.

We have illustrated the capability of the VP FLIR by comparing two modes of imaging with staring focal plane arrays. One mode viewed the object with no scanning and the other mode used micro-step-stare scanning to produce multiple images which were reconstructed into a single frame. In this experimental comparison, only the effective number of pixels across the field-of-view and the detector integration time were varied. All other parameters were kept constant between the two imaging trains.

In future research, other parameters may be varied. It is not yet known what the effects are of tradeoffs between image fidelity and signal-to-noise ratio for object recognition algorithms. Since these two quantities are traded off between the two image modes described above, a more thorough investigation is needed. The VP FLIR offers the ideal tool to conduct this investigation, as well as to further validate the microscan model.

REFERENCES

1. D. J. Bradley and P. N. J. Dennis, "Sampling effects in CdHgTe focal plane arrays," Proc. SPIE Vol. 590, 53-60 (1985).
2. Amber Engineering, Inc., 5756 Thornwood Drive, Goleta, CA 93117-3802, manual for the Series 3000 Infrared Component Test System (August 1991).
3. Amber Engineering, Inc., 5756 Thornwood Drive, Goleta, CA 93117-3802, Pro-View Manual (July 1991).
4. F. O. Huck, N. Halyo, and S. K. Park, "Aliasing and blurring in 2-D sampled imagery," Appl. Opt. 19, 2174-2181 (1980).
5. E. A. Watson, R. A. Muse, and F. P. Blommel, "Aliasing and Blurring in Microscanned Imagery," SPIE Conf. 1689 Infrared Imaging Systems: Design, Analysis, Modeling, and Testing III (April 1992).

Fig. 4. Comparison of microscanned and unscanned imagery. The object is a spoke target. The image on the right is unscanned, and clearly shows the effects of aliasing. The image on the left is the microscanned image, and is a more faithful representation of the object.